

LEGAL BASIS FOR ORGANIZING ELECTIONS TO LOCAL SELF-GOVERNMENT BODIES IN AZERBAIJAN AT THE BEGINNING OF THE XX CENTURY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14947181>

Abstract

Conducting elections is closely connected with the free expression of will of a specific person. In this sense, by expressing his will, a person makes a free choice from an objectively existing colossal variety of individual and special opportunities. Thus, he directly participates not only in the formation of general legal principles of functioning and development of the entire society to which he belongs, but also in the formation of structures of power and management adequate to his own interests and needs, through which norm-setting, law enforcement and other functions are carried out. From this point of view, it is of particular interest how this selective process occurs in different periods of historical development and in different structural formations. This article discusses the legal and organizational aspects of holding elections of city government in our country at the beginning of the last century. Being one of the forms of implementing democracy, local self-government covers not only the political and socio-economic spheres, but also the cultural and educational sphere. The article also covers issues related to the rules for holding elections to city and zemstvo self-government bodies during the functioning of the Special Transcaucasian Committee and the Transcaucasian Commissariat in 1917-1918.

Keywords: elections, local self-government, democracy, city дума, City Regulations, electoral rights, zemstvo, simplified city public self-government.

Peculiarities of normative regulation of elections to local self-government during the period of the Russian Empire's rule in Azerbaijan

The time of the adoption of the draft law on municipal self-government by the highest organs of state power coincided with the period of aggravation of domestic policy and the emerging turning point in the autocracy's views on self-government. In 1904, the Baku mayor A. Novikov wrote about this: "Municipal self-government appeared after the zemstvo. The time was relatively unfavorable. The reaction had not yet begun, but its breath was felt. Naturally, in relatively unfavorable conditions, a not very perfect organization appeared" [16, p.8]. Nevertheless, to a certain extent, the progressiveness of the City Regulations of 1870 consisted in the fact that the class-bureaucratic organs of municipal government were replaced by general-class (representing all classes) organs based on the principle of property qualification. The urban population, although within somewhat limited limits, was given the opportunity to be represented in government.

At the same time, the use of the three-class electoral system adopted from Prussia shaded this progressiveness. Thus, according to the principle of "proportionality" underlying the electoral system, the degree of participation in the work of city self-government was determined by the size of the quitrent and taxes paid to the city treasury. That is, all voters were included in the general list as the taxes paid were reduced, after which they were divided into three categories so that the money paid by voters of each category had to make up a third of all city taxes.

In general, according to the City Regulations of 1870, only males who had reached the age of 25, had a certain property qualification and participated in the payment of city taxes had the right to vote [12, p.211]. At the same time, persons convicted of committing crimes or misdemeanors for which the law provides for

the deprivation of rights of social status or the restriction of these rights, as well as those brought to investigative and judicial actions on charges of committing the said acts (except for those justified by a court sentence), removed from office during the last three years, persons declared bankrupt (except for persons who found themselves in such a situation as a result of an accident), deprived of their clerical rank and rank due to committing offenses in cases stipulated by law, were deprived of voting rights. Those occupying high administrative positions and local police officials, even if they had property qualifications, did not have the right to vote (Articles 18-19). In accordance with Article 20 of the Regulations, women, as well as young men under the age of 25, if they had a property qualification, could transfer the right to participate in voting by proxy to relatives, guardians or trustees [12, p.211]. However, in accordance with Article 23 of the law, no one from the city population could have more than two votes in the elections (one of their own, the other by proxy). Along with individuals, various institutions, structures, societies, companies, firms that took part in the payment of city taxes had the right to vote in the person of their representatives.

In the City Regulations, along with the establishment of privileges for the wealthy part of the population, national inequality was allowed. Thus, the representation of the main part of the local population - non-Christians (that is, Azerbaijanis) could not exceed half of the members of the Duma.

According to the Regulations, persons who received an absolute majority of votes were considered elected to the Duma. In the event of the election of a smaller number of deputies than was provided by law, the election of the missing members of the Duma was established by a relative majority of votes. The total number of members of the Duma, depending on the number of voters, could be from 30 to 72 people. In cities with no more than 300 voters, 30 people were elected as members of the Duma. In addition, for every

150 voters, 6 members of the Duma were allowed to be elected, with the condition that the total number of members of the Duma did not exceed 72 people [4, p.252-253; 12, p.212]. The members of the City Duma were free from any responsibility to the voters. As stated in Article 40 of the City Regulations, voters did not have the right to give the members any instructions (mandates, orders) [5, p.102].

At the same time, elections to city self-government bodies were an important link in the implementation of the city reform, since they directly formed the composition of the elected bodies, which, in turn, predetermined the direction and, in general, the content of municipal activity.

On June 11, 1892, a new City Regulation was approved [9, art. 8708]. The new Regulations further narrowed the composition of the representation in favor of the big bourgeoisie and the nobility and further limited the right of city public administration. The changes made to city government by the reform of 1892 concerned two main areas: 1) reduction of the contingent of voters by increasing the property qualification and 2) strengthening the control of government bodies and institutions over city public administration. The changes made to city government by the reform of 1892 concerned two main areas: 1) reducing the number of voters by increasing the property qualification and 2) strengthening the control of government bodies and institutions over city public administration. The concept of "city society" as a subject of law was excluded from the City Regulations and the concept of "city population" was retained only as an object of management.

True, the City Regulations of 1892, in comparison with the previous Regulations, in principle, slightly changed the powers and scope of activities of city government bodies, but legitimized the intervention of the governor in all matters of city public administration. Thus, Article 119 of the Regulations provided that if the governor did not approve the persons elected to the positions of the head of the municipality, members of the municipal government and the city secretary, or the elections were not held, then repeat elections should be held with the condition that persons not approved by the governor would not be put to the vote. If the elections failed for the second time, or the newly elected persons were again not approved by the governor, these positions were filled by persons appointed by the governor. The provincial administration had the right to apply disciplinary measures against officials of the city public administration, including their removal from office. According to Article 11 of the Regulations of 1892, the governor exercised control not only over the legality and correctness of the activities of city councils and administrations, but also over the appropriateness of these activities. The provincial court for city affairs had the right to discuss the legality and correctness of any decision and order of self-government bodies. Instructions for the executive bodies of city government, rules for managing city property and capital, decisions on the alienation of city real estate and other similar acts entered into legal force only after approval by the governor.

The City Regulations of 1892 abolished another of the previous rules, that is, the procedure for dividing

voters into categories, and provided for the organization of one election meeting for all voters. In the case of a large number of voters, the possibility of electing members of the Duma in precincts was established. In this case, members of the Duma could be elected by voters of each individual precinct, as a result of which passive electoral rights were significantly limited. The right to vote was granted only to those individuals and institutions (government agencies, charitable societies, schools and scientific institutions) in the city that, for at least one year, owned real estate worth between 300 and 3,000 rubles (established depending on the importance of the city and the size of its population. Thus, for the population of the city of Baku, it was envisaged to own property worth at least 1,500 rubles, and for the population of Ganja - at least 1,000 rubles), as well as companies, societies and individuals maintaining first or second-class commercial and industrial enterprises within the city [9, art. 8708; 12, p.217]). And this meant a departure from the principle of participation of the entire population in the representative body of the city established by the previous law and a maximum limitation of the circle of voters. In accordance with Article 22 of the Regulation and the Supplement to the Regulation (the "Rules on Simplified Urban Public Administration"), in cities where simplified public administration was envisaged, instead of the City Duma, which had dozens of members, a city assembly of authorized representatives consisting of 12-15 people was established. Authorized representatives were elected at meetings of local homeowners from among persons who owned real estate worth at least 100 rubles. Clause 2 of the Supplement to Article 22 of the Regulation did not provide for the general everyday understanding of the word "homeowner", that is, the head of the family, the manager of the family household, but for persons who had a property qualification in the form of a house within the city limits. The reduction of the property qualification from 300 to 100 rubles, in theory, should have increased the number of voters, but the use of restrictions on the use of the electoral right prevented this to a certain extent. In the "Instructions for the organization of simplified city public administrations", approved by the Ministry of Internal Affairs on May 30, 1893, issues related to the electoral process became even more specific. The assembly of authorized representatives elected the city headman (elder, kedkhuda, head, rais) and his assistant (if the governor considered it necessary - two assistants. No restrictions were introduced for Muslims to fill these positions; moreover, by the decree of the Governing Senate of April 24, 1901, in the event of the election of persons professing Islam as city elders, governors were recommended to approve them for this position [13, p.574].

In general, simplified public administration at first limited collegiality in the management of city affairs, reducing the size of the property qualification, increased the number of city voters, while at the same time depriving them of the right to make binding decisions and change city plans.

By the decision of the State Council of May 29, 1895, the City Regulations of 1892 extended to the cities of the South Caucasus, including Azerbaijan, in re-

spect of which the self-government reform was not applied by the previous law [13, p.10-11]. However, the creation of city dumas in Azerbaijan was planned only in Baku, Ganja (Yelizavetpol) and Shusha, in other district cities - Shamakhi, Lankaran, Guba, Nukha (Sheki), Nakhchivan, Ordubad, the creation of simplified public self-government bodies was envisaged. It should be noted that before the application of public self-government in all district cities of Azerbaijan and in the provincial city of Ganja, the city economy was handled by a special department for city affairs, which functioned in Ganja under the city police, and in other cities - under local district police departments. In their practical activities, they were guided by the "Regulations on the economy of cities, where the City Regulations were not applied" and the "Charter on the City Economy" [10, art. 809]. The main functions of these departments were to draw up annual budgets for city revenues and expenses, submitted for discussion to the provincial government.

However, simplified self-government bodies, even after the Regulations of 1892, were not used in all district centers of Azerbaijan. For example, in the centers of Javad and Goychay districts, district police departments continued to deal with urban management during that period; for this purpose, district departments for urban affairs were created under them, chaired by district chiefs and consisting of their assistants, city police officers and deputies elected from of the local population. The legislation of this period provided for certain differences for large and small cities on the issue of establishing city self-government, the procedure for its interaction with state authorities, the limits of authority of local self-government bodies, in general, which was regarded by a number of prominent lawyers of that time as a certain injustice in relation to small cities; in order to eliminate this injustice, some even proposed creating a special council for city and zemstvo affairs under the committee of ministers [6, p. 483].

According to the requirements of Article 56 of the City Regulations of 1892, the number of members of the Baku City Duma was to be up to 80, the Ganja City Duma - up to 60, and the Shusha City Duma - up to 40 people (according to the established general procedure, if the total number of city voters did not exceed 100 people, the number of members was set at 20 people, and for every 50 voters over 100 people, 3 members were included in the composition) [9, art. 8708]. In fact, the Baku and Ganja City Dumas were allocated fewer seats than stipulated by law (54 and 40, respectively).

In accordance with Article 47 of the City Regulations (as amended in 1906), elections to the Duma, conducted using balls, based on decisions of city Dumas were allowed to be replaced by voting using registration sheets (ballots), which, as envisaged, were subject to personal presentation by voters at a mass meeting to the chairmen of the election meetings [10, art. 942]. These voting sheets were filled out by voters either directly at election meetings, or in advance and in folded form they were dropped into a special ballot box. The sheets indicated the persons for whom the voter voted. The persons who received the greatest number of votes

were considered elected to the Duma. In the event of a tie, the voting results were determined by drawing lots.

The law "On the establishment of temporary rules related to the creation of city councils and meetings of authorized representatives in the cities of the Caucasus region" [1, art. 865; 13, pp. 152-153], adopted on May 15, 1899 specifically for the cities of the Caucasus, the rights of city self-government still more restricted. In this law, which included temporary measures until the legislative revision of decisions on the procedure for creating city councils and authorized meetings, the rights of administrative management were further expanded, in particular, the head of the civil part in the Caucasus was allowed, at his own discretion, to exclude any persons from the composition elected as members of the city council and authorized representatives.

The publication of such a special law for the cities of the Caucasus, the distrust of the city public administration and the establishment of strict control over it directed the election campaign in a completely different direction - the aggravation of relations between local clans and ethnic groups on this basis, as a result, "the feud connected with the "brotherly massacre in the city elections" was used by obsolete elements. Instead of the former young progressive representatives of the intelligentsia, city administrations were headed by people from a completely different "opera" [10, art. 35].

Article 44 of the City Regulations of 1892, prohibiting the number of non-Christian members of the Duma from exceeding 1/3 of the total composition [9, art. 8708], as an expression of unequal treatment of the population professing Islam (Azerbaijanis), included norms that caused the most intense disputes. The incorrectness of this article made itself known in practice. Thus, due to the violation of the electoral rights of the Muslim population, whose numbers in most cities of the South Caucasus (Baku, Ganja, Irevan, Shamakhi, Guba, Nukha, Lankaran, Nakhchivan, Yenibayazit, Shusha, etc.) were several times greater than the Christian population, petitions were constantly filed before higher authorities to go beyond the limits of the specified norm. As G.M. Tumanov noted, "in all these cities, the Muslim population had long since adopted Russian culture, and there was no serious reason to deprive it of equality with Christians in matters of self-government" [21, pp.185-186].

On December 14, 1900, a change was made to Article 44 of the City Regulations, and, according to the new edition, it was established that in the cities of the Caucasus region the number of non-Christian councilors cannot exceed half of the composition of the Duma members. In cities where the implementation of this order was unacceptable and difficult from the point of view of local conditions, the decision of the city and zemstvo local self-government or the local government for city affairs to go beyond this order was allowed with the consent of the Minister of Internal Affairs [13, p. 142].

In order to ensure equality and lift restrictions, on January 25, 1905, Azerbaijani deputies in the Baku City Duma proposed that the Duma adopt a resolution on filing a petition with the administrative leadership in connection with the equalization of rights of Muslims

of the South Caucasus with other residents of the empire in all bodies of city self-government, the release of city self-government from administrative guardianship, the granting of voting rights to tenants who pay housing taxes, the establishment of a minimum educational qualification, if not for voters, then at least for those elected, and recommended calling on all other city administrations of the South Caucasus to join this petition. The Duma adopted a decision on these proposals [7, f.50, inv.1, case 260, p.28-37]. By the decision adopted by the Baku City Duma and the provincial department for urban affairs on November 12, 1910, a petition was filed with the Caucasian administration to hold elections to the Duma without applying restrictions for Azerbaijanis. In response to this, the Viceroy of the Caucasus, in a letter dated January 28, 1911, addressed to the Baku City Administration, permitted elections of members to the City Duma for 1911-1915 "without observing the procedure established by Article 44 of the City Regulations of 1892 on limiting the number of members from non-Christians to half of the Duma" [8, f.13, inv.2, case 714, p.4]. However, on the eve of the elections, this permission was revoked by the vicegerency.

From numerous archival data it becomes known that the elections to the Dumas and simplified public self-government bodies held in other cities of Azerbaijan were also accompanied by various violations of the law, which were directed mainly against the interests of the local urban population, that against the background of the restrictions imposed by the authorities, voters showed complete indifference to this process, that, ultimately, the elections were held again several times, as they were declared invalid, and their results, being recognized as invalid, were canceled.

As a result of the analysis of this information, it becomes clear that after the application of the second provision, the wealthiest city residents-owners were allowed to participate in the elections to local self-government bodies, therefore the assertion about the representation of the interests of the urban population in the city self-government (with the exception of some progressively minded representatives of the Azerbaijani intelligentsia elected to the Duma at that time) seems unconvincing.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the issue of improving the local self-government system throughout the country was repeatedly raised in government circles, and a number of changes were even made to the current legislation on local self-government. However, during this period, that is, until the end of February 1917, the development and adoption, as envisaged, of new legislation related to city self-government did not occur.

Legal acts that changed the conduct of elections in the South Caucasus after the collapse of the autocratic empire

An important place among the laws developed by the meeting on the reform of local self-government was occupied by the Provisional Government on April 15, 1917, "Temporary Rules on the Election of Public City Dumas and on Precinct City Administrations" [8,

f.1818, inv. 1, case 303, pp.21-24]. In connection with the application of these rules, on May 3, the Ministry of Internal Affairs prepared and approved "Instructions for city public administrations" [8, f.1818, inv.1, case 303, pp.24a-28].

The temporary rules for the first time provided for the application of general, direct and equal suffrage during elections to city self-government bodies throughout the country as a whole. In accordance with Article 3 of the Rules, citizens of the country of both sexes, regardless of nationality and religious affiliation, who had reached the age of 20, residing in the relevant city at the time of application of the electoral lists or running a household in the given city or having official duties, as well as other employment related to the city, had the right to participate in the elections. Persons in military service participated in elections on a general basis. At the same time, persons convicted by the court for crimes in the area of electoral law and property crimes were deprived of their voting rights for a year after the end of their sentence, those sentenced to such types of punishment as deprivation of rights of social status or restriction of these rights - for three years after the end of their sentence, and brothel keepers were deprived of their voting rights altogether.

Unlike active voting rights, passive voting rights were enjoyed not only by persons who lived within the city limits, had official duties or other employment, but also by persons who had no connection with the city (in the event of compliance with other requirements provided for participation in elections). Voters were granted the right, no later than ten days before the elections, to submit to the mayor a list of candidates for members of the city who wished to be elected and who had been put to the vote. The number of candidates indicated in the list should not exceed the total number of councilors subject to election in a given city. Each voter had to sign only one of the lists of candidates for members of the city. To conduct elections of members, a city election commission was formed under the chairmanship of the city mayor. The commission, upon invitation of the mayor, included three people from among the voters. At the same time, the commission from each group of voters that submitted lists of candidates for the council included the person who first signed the list (if the persons who were part of the group of voters did not elect a special person among themselves).

When conducting elections by precincts, in addition to the city election commission, a precinct election commission was also provided for each polling station. The city mayor, at his own discretion, chaired one of these commissions. The chairmen of other election commissions were invited by the city mayor from among the voters. The composition of the precinct election commission included three people invited by its chairman from among the voters. In addition, the commission included a person elected among themselves by each group of voters who submitted lists of candidates for members.

The elections were conducted by means of a ballot sheet by secret ballot for only one of the lists of candidates for the vowels. Each ballot sheet had to indicate the number of the list of candidates for the vowels for which the voter had to cast his vote. The sheets were

placed by voters in opaque single-color envelopes made by the city administration and having no signs except for its seal, sealed and personally handed to its chairman at an open meeting of the commission. These envelopes were dropped by the chairman of the commission into a sealed ballot box in the presence of voters. The total number of voters to be elected in the electoral district was divided between the lists of candidates in proportion to the number of votes cast in the elections for each of these lists. In accordance with Article 25 of the provisional regulations, in order to establish the number of deputies allocated to each of the submitted lists of candidates, the total number of deputies to be elected was multiplied by the number of votes cast for the relevant list and divided by the number of votes cast for all lists in the electoral district as a whole. The quotient of this division determined the number of voters elected on each list. From each list, in the order in which candidates were included, persons were included in the composition of deputies in a quantity corresponding to the results of the above-mentioned division.

At the end of the elections, all documents, including voting sheets, were sent to a high-ranking representative of the local administrative authority within two days. He, in turn, could protest the election process and its results in the appropriate instance of the administrative court within seven days. In addition, complaints related to illegal actions committed by persons participating in the elections could be filed with the administrative court within three days. In accordance with the Resolution of the Provisional Government "On Administrative Courts" [7, f.389, inv.1, case 765, pp.82-83], seven days from the date of acceptance of the relevant documents were established for the consideration of protests and complaints by the administrative court. If, as a result of such a judicial review, a conclusion was made on the irregularity of the elections as a whole, the court made a decision to cancel the election results. The city administration, having received a court decision related to this issue, had to make a decision to hold new elections within a month. Although the decision made by the court, motivated by the irregularity of both the election results as a whole and the election of individual members, was sent for proceedings, nevertheless, the law (article 32) also provided for the right to appeal this decision within a month in the Governing Senate.

Despite the innovations introduced by the law "On City Public Administration" in the area of democratization of city dumas, these structures, nevertheless, were heavily dependent on the central government and its local commissioners. The city dumas failed to restructure their work. Only the composition of the dumas and boards was changed. Thus, even before the new official elections, political parties and non-party citizens included "social democratic elements" in their composition without prior agreement. A certain change has also occurred in the status of the Baku City Duma. There was a gradual democratization of this institution of power with its involvement in political struggle. As a result, 12 different parties and groups [18, 20.10.1917] were registered to participate in its new elections.

It should also be noted that although the programs of all the parties participating in the elections, in the part concerning the procedure for holding municipal

elections, along with holding elections to local self-government bodies by secret ballot, also approved direct elections, nevertheless, there were certain fundamental differences. Thus, if, due to the coincidence of the socialist bloc, consisting of the Socialist Revolutionaries and Mensheviks, and the programs of the Musavat party and the Committee of Muslim Public Organizations, which participated in the elections on a single list, planned to implement their municipal programs under the conditions of the existing system, then the Bolsheviks in their programs declared the transfer of political power into the hands of the proletariat as the most important goal.

Despite the fact that the laws "On the conduct of elections of city дума members" and "On amendments to the current Regulation on public administration of cities" reflected a number of progressive features, nevertheless, gross violations were allowed in the course of their application, and even deviations from the content of the law were encountered. Thus, the 120-thousand population of the industrial and factory districts of Baku, sailors and employees of railway lines were deprived of participation in the elections to the city дума. The compilation of the lists of voters was assigned to the city government - a body interested in delaying the elections. In this regard, although the law allocated two weeks from the moment of the announcement of the aforementioned law for the compilation of the lists of voters, nevertheless, the Baku city government announced the possibility of holding the elections to the city дума no earlier than 6 months later. As a result, the deadline established by law was not met, and the elections to the Duma were held on October 29, 1917. Although no party managed to achieve a decisive majority in the elections, nevertheless, for the first time, national democratic forces were able to obtain a sufficient number of seats in the Baku city self-government.

Unlike Russia, where the old pre-revolutionary institutions of governance were gradually abolished from the end of 1917, in the South Caucasus there was a tendency to resume work on the project of reforming zemstvo self-government. Despite the functioning of revolutionary committees and the system of councils in a number of regions at that time, in Azerbaijan, nevertheless, the consistent development of the principles of territorial self-government could be clearly seen in the example of district self-government, established by the "Temporary Regulation on Zemstvo Institutions in the South Caucasus" of the Transcaucasian Commissariat of January 25, 1918 [8, f.1818, inv.1, case 261, pp.101-165]. Thus, in accordance with Article 9 of the law, it was planned to create a separate zemstvo unit (with the rights of a district zemstvo) for the city of Baku (within the city's mayoralty), and a second district zemstvo unit for other territories of the Baku district, including industrial areas [7, f.389, inv.1, case 765, pp.53]. It was established to entrust the City Duma and the administration with the management of affairs within the city (in this case, the city дума exercised the powers of the district zemstvo assembly, and the city government exercised the powers of the district zemstvo administration) [8, f.1818, inv.1, case 261, pp.106-107]. On January 25, 1918, the Transcaucasian Commissariat also

adopted the "Instruction on holding volost, district and provincial elections in the South Caucasus."

The temporary regulations differed significantly from the regulations adopted earlier in connection with the zemstvos, relied more on democratic principles, and abolished the previous numerous qualifications. Thus, all citizens who had reached the age of 20, regardless of their nationality and religion, who lived or owned a house within the boundaries of the corresponding vilage or city on the eve of the compilation of the electoral lists and the introduction of amendments to them, or who were in a certain service in the given territory or had connections with this territory in connection with one or another employment, could participate in the elections of zemstvo councilors. Passive voting rights could also be used by persons who did not have the specified connection with the corresponding territory.

In general, the "Regulations on zemstvo institutions in the South Caucasus" can be divided into two parts: 1) the procedure for electing zemstvo councilors; 2) the scope and limits of powers of zemstvo institutions. The "General Provisions" reflected in the first section of the law basically included the contents of the relevant part of the laws on zemstvo institutions adopted by the Provisional Government (with the exception of amendments and additions to a number of articles in connection with the local characteristics of the Transcaucasian region).

As for the procedure for holding elections of zemstvo members, a number of distinctive features can be observed in this issue in comparison with Russian legislation. Thus, in Russian legislation, the formation of volost zemstvo institutions was regulated by one law, and the procedure for holding elections of provincial and district zemstvo members was regulated by another, as a result of which they provided for different electoral rules. Elections of provincial and district zemstvo members were held according to the proportional electoral system. The electoral lists submitted at the time indicated both the number of the list for which the vote was cast and the list of nominated candidates. Only in urban settlements, where less than three district councilors were elected, was it envisaged to vote for each candidate separately. The elections of volost councilors were conducted in accordance with the law of May 21, 1917 and the instruction of June 11, 1917 on the majoritarian electoral system. In this case, voting was conducted using voting sheets, which included the names, surnames and pseudonyms of the intended candidates, and the votes were counted using special cards created for each candidate separately. In accordance with the resolution of June 26 and the instruction of September 23, 1917, in a number of provinces of the country, the conduct of elections to volost zemstvos was based on a proportional system.

In the South Caucasus, the procedure for holding elections of volost, district and provincial zemstvo councillors was united in a single normative act, so many repetitive norms were excluded from the law and replaced with references to the relevant articles, which included the procedure for holding volost zemstvo elections. Thus, a decision was made to hold elections of councillors to volost, district and provincial zemstvo

assemblies in accordance with the procedure for holding elections to the Constituent Assembly (based on the proportional electoral system), that is, by the tested population, using a method familiar to it. In order to facilitate and speed up the compilation of voter lists, it was considered appropriate to use the voter lists compiled for the election of members to the Constituent Assembly (by making additions and amendments in connection with possible changes in the rights of voters from the day of elections to the Constituent Assembly until the elections of zemstvo councilors - to for example, the inclusion of new voters, the exclusion of a number of voters from the list as a result of their loss of voting rights, etc.) Also by a resolution of the Transcaucasian Commissariat of November 28 1917 provided for the immediate application of both volost and district and provincial zemstvos.

According to the specified normative acts, it was considered expedient, while preserving the proportional electoral system, allowing political minorities to obtain seats in lower zemstvos, to amend the procedure for its implementation, that is, to conduct voting not on the basis of electoral lists, but by means of balls for each candidate individually, since when voting by means of electoral lists, political parties had more opportunity to dictate their position to ordinary citizens. When voting with balls, elections take on an individual character, that is, candidates are elected not by belonging to a particular party, but by personal merits. In the course of such an individual electoral procedure, the voter does not fall under the influence of the lists of candidates dictated to him, on the contrary, he independently places a ball for each candidate, while the candidate's belonging to a particular list does not play a special role. This procedure was the most favorable, in particular, during the elections of the vowels of the volost zemstvos, when the polling stations were small, and the voter personally knew, if not all, then most of the candidates and had the opportunity to make an independent choice among them, without referring to the electoral lists. On the other hand, the procedure for holding elections by means of balls was also used during the previous city and zemstvo regulations, their experience showed that, unlike voting according to pre-prepared lists of candidates, in elections held according to the specified procedure, attempts by parties to put pressure on voters failed.

If the impossibility of applying the "Temporary Regulations on Zemstvo Institutions in the South Caucasus" [8, f.1818, inv.1, case 261, pp.101-165] in Baku and a number of territories included in the Baku province during that period was connected with the seizure of power by the Bolsheviks in these territories and the organization by the Bolshevik-Dashnak formations of mass slaughter of Azerbaijanis on national grounds to strengthen this power, then in other regions of Azerbaijan the implementation of this law was connected with completely different reasons. Thus, during the period of activity of the Transcaucasian Sejm, which was more concerned with issues of a political nature, negotiations conducted in connection with the regulation of national issues and territorial disputes, regulation of the activities of central government bodies, as well as the resolution of agrarian issues, no significant attention was paid

to the application of zemstvo self-government in these territories. The collapse of the Transcaucasian Sejm and the proclamation of independence by Azerbaijan determined the inevitability of the resumption, after a certain break, of normative-legal and practical activities related to the implementation of zemstvo self-government.

Conclusion

The changes reflected in the electoral system of city self-government institutions as a result of the second city reform once again demonstrated that in the course of "improving" the legislation, the government was guided no longer by proposals from the localities and data from law enforcement practice, but by its own considerations, the essence of which was the desire to prevent excessive activity of local society.

From a legal point of view, a serious shortcoming of the normative base of local self-government was the insufficiently consistent implementation of the principle of establishing the boundaries of executive and administrative powers, and this also applies to the electoral system in the sphere of local self-government. At the same time, the practical side of the existence and activity of self-government institutions at that time demonstrated their viability and, to a certain extent, universality in solving both state and, in particular, local problems.

The Provisional Government, as well as the Transcaucasian Commissariat, in their innovations attempted to act in the direction of pan-European standards of organizing local self-government and implement new reforms based on bourgeois principles. It is quite possible that the bourgeois-democratic government in its model took as a basis the "middle line", the most acceptable for the structure of local self-government throughout the country. Having assigned new state functions to local self-government bodies, the government simultaneously set the goal of creating guarantees for their independence and ensuring the formation of these bodies from local residents through elections.

Despite the preparation of local self-government reforms (both urban and zemstvo) without taking into account the socio-political situation in the country and the impossibility, in this context, of their successful completion, nevertheless, the legal framework created in this area can be assessed, in any case, as a historical and legal achievement. It is in this regard that the experience of developing in previous times by legislators and lawyers a new legal sphere for Azerbaijan - municipal law should not be left out of attention in the formation, improvement and development of the legal framework of the modern system of local self-government. It should also be noted that the legal force of the above-studied normative legal acts related to the conduct of elections to local self-government bodies was preserved in the early days of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic during a certain period (transitional period). After some time, the founders of the Republic, using the accumulated scientific, theoretical and empirical materials in the field of local self-government in organizing and improving the system of governance of the state that had declared its independence, prepared a legal basis based on democratic and universal values to

ensure the effective operation of self-government institutions in accordance with their purpose.

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